

Three-Term Political Discourse

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ABSTRACT: Presidential elections and political issues in Indonesia are currently experiencing various very significant dynamics. In this case of presidential elections, the people have the right to vote in elections. 2024 is the next democratic year for the people of the Republic of Indonesia because this year the term of office of the President and Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia for the 2019-2024 period will end or continue until three terms. This is a pro and con by looking at some of the history of other countries in the previous year. Seeing this phenomenon, researchers are interested in researching and looking at the three-period political discourse in Indonesia. The method used in this article is a literature study whose research object is in the form of literature works, either in the form of scientific journals, books, articles, or pre-existing data. The results of research conducted on the political discourse of the three-term presidential term; researchers draw the conclusion that the discourse on the extension of the presidential term has become a debate. The three-term political discourse gave rise to responses from various parties, both support and rejection, but this is still only in the form of a discourse and there is no certainty.

KEYWORDS: three-term political, Politics, Presidential

INTRODUCTION

Presidential elections and political issues in Indonesia are currently experiencing various very significant dynamics. In this case of presidential elections, the people have the right to vote in elections. 2024 is the next democratic year for the people of the Republic of Indonesia because this year the term of office of the President and Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia for the 2019-2024 period will end or continue until three terms. This is a pro and con by looking at some of the history of other countries in the previous year.

Yudhistira (2020) said in his research regarding the limit of the president's term of office to a maximum of two terms and political officials created in the Presidential Election system in the United States, George Washington as the first President at that time made an unwritten policy when he refused to hold his third term in 1796. In his research, it was stated that afterwards Franklin D. Roosevelt was the one who used the legal vacuum regarding the office of president in the United States and won the presidential election 4 times from 1932 to 1944, then after the death of Franklin D. Roosevelt who was then the President of the United States created a limit of only two terms in the 22nd Amendment to the United States Constitution in 1951. This then provides valuable experiences and lessons in several other countries.

The constitutional history that occurred in the United States at that time can also be a lesson for Indonesia, which is also currently facing almost the same problem. However, what has happened in the constitutional history of the United States is proof that provisions that are prone to being politicized in order to perpetuate power, if not strictly regulated, will create loopholes for politicians to perpetuate existing power continuously. Limiting the president's term of office to a maximum of two terms is quite important because if it is not restricted, it will allow abuse of authority in the next political period.

This three-term political discourse has become a lot of discussion in the community. Discourse is a communication in the form of oral discourse as a form of communication delivered orally or through oral media and written discourse as a form of communication delivered in writing or with written media (Fadli, 2018). Meanwhile, according to Rauf & Rado (2022) politics is a science about constitutionality which includes the system of government, the basics of government, all affairs, and actions regarding state government or towards other countries and how to act in dealing with problems and carrying out policies.

Recently, political discourse related to the election of presidential and vice-presidential candidates for the 2024 – 2029 period is developing, especially in social media. The discourse related to the general election of candidates for the head of state seems to be inexhaustible from the pros and cons by the people in Indonesia regarding the general election. In addition, elections are also an important instrument where elections function as a filtering tool for political officials who will represent and carry the people's vote within representative institutions (Almanar & Rusnin, 2022). Therefore, the existence of political parties is intended to activate,

represent common interests, provide avenues for opposing opinions, and provide a means of succession to political leadership. According to Rahman, Et al (2017) a political party is an organization that coordinates candidates to compete in elections in a country.

Political events such as new political elections are some of the events that are quite interesting to research because they only happen once every five years. The discourse related to political events that currently exist is related to Joko Widodo's three-term politics which is widespread on social media. Every discourse on social media has a certain purpose, one of which is the delivery of people's desires and aspirations. Social media has become a source of information that is inseparable from people's lives today. Social media, which has become a necessity in people's daily lives, explains that people can no longer be separated from the social media internet.

According to Hajiza & Santoso (2022) for a long time the relationship between social media and the world of politics in Indonesia has been a lot of public attention, this is because social media is a means of political communication that connects the government and society. Social media is the main media in the process of delivering messages to the general public where there are several types of social media that will be used regularly, namely Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram (Senova, 2016). The role of social media is quite large in influencing the level of popularity of the president or members of the 3-term politics, where almost all people know the information of the three-term political candidate so that his character has been formed by the public. However, it is likely that some people do not know the character of the future leader of the three periods more deeply and only see news from social media.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this article is a literature study whose research object is in the form of literature works, either in the form of scientific journals, books, articles, or pre-existing data. The literature is used to complement the research conducted by the author, namely regarding three-period political discourse and the type of data used is secondary data. The nature of this article is descriptive analysis, where the researcher provides education and understanding to the reader.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this article, researchers discuss the discourse of how three-period political discourse, how social media is used as propaganda and a liaison between the community and the government regarding political problems in Indonesia. Various social media such as twitter, Facebook and Instagram are often used to lead opinions and political conversations as well as the discourse of president Joko Widodo's three-term term. This has caused various diverse responses from the community in the form of support or rejection. Although it is still in the form of discourse, it has generated many responses from the Indonesian people.

Responses from the public on some social media that the type of political issues that exist. The discourse is inaccurate about the information or news being spread, this type of discourse is usually unknown to the identity of the disseminator who spreads the circulating information and leads to various opinions or propaganda. Propaganda refers to the role of propaganda to control public opinion with implied and symbolic messages, to speak more concretely is carried out through stories, rumors, reports, images that are uncertain of their accuracy (Ahmad Zakiyudin, 2018). Propaganda here as a strategy carried out to accompany opinions or general opinions by groups or individuals who have a certain interest to achieve the desired goal. Political propaganda today is mostly carried out using current technology such as social media.

Social media is a medium on the internet that allows its users to interact, cooperate, share information, and communicate with other users and form social bonds through the internet (Puspitarini & Nuraeni, 2019). Social media at this time has become a large organization that accommodates groups of individuals or groups from various regions into one in cyberspace, members of this organization live and interact online like residents in a country, although between them do not know each other let alone have emotional ties in real life (Nugraha, 2019). Social media such as Instagram, Facebook and twitter are quite effective media for doing propaganda. With this, Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter are most widely used by irresponsible people by spreading messages by building sometimes inaccurate conversations such as political propaganda.

Political propaganda has a very close relationship with sometimes inaccurate conversations. When making the public believe in whatever happens, the main topic that is used as a topic with the sentences used is as it is in this three-period political discourse. It was in these sentences that later became political propaganda and gave rise to various responses, namely by making the President

a reference in it. Propaganda or opinions that exist in the public such as social media can influence others in determining attitudes (Ardiansyah, 2019).

This is in line with research conducted by Palupi, (2019) which found the results that Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter as social media are quite popular in parts of the world and even Indonesia so that it will be easy to convey short messages which will then give rise to various public opinions. In a short message circulating on social media there is no citing sources so the political message and conversation become hotter like a three-term political discourse. The discourse is inseparable from positive and negative comments from public figures who are both pro and contra to the existence of a three-term discourse of the President of Indonesia.

According to Padli (2021) The President as the head of government has the authority to appoint and dismiss ministers and the formation of a cabinet and the powers of the President do not require approval from other branches of power. Based on this with the breadth of the president's authority, so it becomes very natural that many of the people want to limit the authority of the president. In this case, the response and opinion of the community is very necessary to participate in the general election without any coercion from other parties later. The participation of the public in providing opinions will determine the fate of Indonesia in the future if the three-term political discourse is truly realized. Amaliah, Et al (2015) in her research stated that community participation in providing responses related to political discourse, one of which is from nearby colleagues who have a considerable influence such as neighbors, family members, and relatives can influence to participate in a political activity. This is also in line with research conducted by Hasan (2020) that voter behavior in the presidential candidate election has four influences that determine the behavior of community voters, namely the influence of ethnic religion, family, friends around, and social media. In this case, it can be concluded that people around and social media also affect voter behavior in elections.

In a general election, voters before deciding their choice will usually get information both from other people and social media, in this case voters should see the candidate they will choose in detail so that voters can get to know more deeply and the mistake of choosing a candidate can be minimized (Muhaimin & Ginting, 2019). In Indonesia, there can still be many reports about conflicts that occur within society related to political issues. This is interpreted as a result of the existing political system which is experiencing problems, one of which is problems related to three-term political discourse. Related to the three-term political discourse, it is also closely related to the MPR.

According to Asnawi (2020) The People's Consultative Assembly (MPR) is a legislative institution which is one of the state's high institutions in the Indonesian constitutional system, thus the decisions issued by the MPR are the main policy in all areas of state life in accordance with the ideals and spiritual principles of the Indonesian nation. Pin, Et al (2021) in his research revealed that if the MPR in 1999 could change the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia with article 7 which specifies the maximum limit of the President's term of office, then if one day most of the Indonesian people want the President's term of office to be changed to three terms, of course changes can be made considering the common interest, because any changes will be possible if conditions and situations permit for the common good. As according to Santika & Sujana (2021), the People's Consultative Assembly (MPR) also has the authority to amend and enact the 1945 Constitution.

However, this is inseparable from other considerations such as community support and enthusiasm. Behind the three-term political discourse, it will still return to the subject of the president himself whether he has the will or spirit, then by itself the president can continue the three-term term or still refer to article 7 of the current 1945 Constitution, which is about the presidential term of office only a maximum of two terms.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted on the political discourse of the three-term presidential term, researchers draw the conclusion that the discourse on the extension of the presidential term of office has become a debate. The three-term political discourse gave rise to responses from various parties, both support and rejection, but this is still only in the form of a discourse and there is no certainty.

1. It is recommended to the social media community, especially Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, to be more careful and careful in understanding the existing sentences or opinions so that they are not easily influenced by things that lead to negative opinions.
2. It is recommended to the government or politics to immediately provide a response regarding the certainty of the truth of the existing discourse.

3. It is suggested to subsequent researchers to complement this study by adding community behavior related to responses to three-term political discourse.

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